

RESOURCE ROOM: IMPLICATIONS FOR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to present the relevance of the resource room for students with special needs. To achieve this objective, it was verified what studies on special education, training of teachers of specialized educational services and resource room point out. This is a bibliographical study, which brings the laws and official documents that govern special education, as well as analyzes in articles, published from 1988 to 2020. The considerations woven throughout this research point out that there is still a need for training for professionals who work in this area, considering that the training of professionals who work in the educational process needs to be continuous, in the sense of improving knowledge and, mainly, educational practices. The research results also point out that the resource rooms provide development in individualized trajectories, also corroborating for the exercises of practices in social contexts. The purpose of the resource rooms is to create a school that learns through the study of challenging and

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overcoming situations. It can never be interpreted as an open space to receive children with some difficulty, where differentiated work can be developed, with a view to including them in school; because the idea of inclusion should be like what Levi Vygotsky (1896-1934) advocated, social inclusion, that is, making the individual able to live his life fully and with less dependence on others; enjoying their existence, with dignity, just like everyone else and among them. In addition to what has been exposed so far, it is concluded that it is necessary to understand resource rooms as a place that seeks to guarantee the necessary support for students with special needs.

Keywords: Special Education. Teaching-learning. Specialized Educational Service. Resource room.

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education is a form of learning, which seeks to equalize the possibilities for all students to learn and grasp the systematic contents proposed in school curricula. It is extremely relevant and necessary with regard to the development process of students who are the target audience for Special Education (PAEE), because these individuals, as a rule, do not have the same intellectual condition to absorb the curricular contents, with the the same ease with which others appear.

Therefore, it is essential to understand the benefits offered to these students through the resource room for their cognitive development. In this space, objects, toys, pedagogical instruments and audiovisual resources are installed, all with the purpose of encouraging maximum intellectual performance in students with specific needs, through teaching experiences, conducted under the guidance of teachers with in-depth knowledge on the subject.

This research takes as its starting point the following questions: What do the laws and official documents say about Special Education? How can the ongoing and ongoing training of teachers contribute to specialized educational services? What are the didactic and pedagogical contributions of the resource room for students with special needs?

The general objective of this study is to present the relevance of the resource room for the educational development of students with special needs. To achieve this objective, we also seek to verify what studies indicate on the use of resource rooms for students with special needs and their results.

This is a bibliographic study, which brings the laws and official documents that govern special education, as well as analyzes of articles published from 1988 to 2020, considering the main approaches to the topic in question.

This research is justified by the need to understand the resource room as an environment that facilitates the teaching and learning process, aimed at the target audience of Special Education.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

After the first half of the 20th Century, due to the intensification of social movements against all forms of prejudice and discrimination that prevented people with special needs from exercising their citizenship in a full and dignified manner, the defense of an inclusive society emerged. Based on this principle, struggles are intensified throughout this historical period and criticism of homogenizing models of teaching and learning is strengthened, models that generate intense exclusion in school spaces.

Based on this ideal, inclusive education, over the years, has become an essential tool for society, as it plays an important role within the school context, focusing on meeting the specific needs of each student, specifically those who, for reasons beyond their control, could be excluded from teaching and classroom interaction.

In the conception of Abramowicz et al. (2011, p. 94), Brazilian schools still present resistance regarding the inclusion of students with specific needs, because there is, in their thinking, a legacy of a *sui generis* type of individual development, based on the industrial ideology that, for so long, was responsible for determining the guidelines for the type of man one wanted to build through formal education, which gave rise to a vision of education based on “[...] the imposition of knowledge, rationality, aesthetics, a unique epistemic subject, legitimized as hegemonic, as a unique parameter of measurement, knowledge, learning and training”.

This idealized format persists in the social imagination and, even though many advances have been made in modeling a society that is inclusive and receptive to all, without much distinction, breaking with such paradigms is still reflected as a challenging action and, only through the knowledge achieved through experience, which proves capable of proving and confirming the abilities of these individuals and how to enhance them in such a way that they can enjoy social coexistence without any type of prejudice or value judgment regarding their capabilities.

It is in this aspect that resource rooms present themselves as privileged learning places, not only for children, but also for everyone involved and for educational sciences and psychological sciences. It's not about pushing the child to overcome their limits and then turning

this into a trophy to be displayed; It is about discovering how to lead them to produce synapses and make logical connections that help them overcome their limitations, conditioned by their particular health situations, physical, psychological and neurological.

The purpose of the resource rooms is to create a school that learns through the study of challenging and overcoming situations. It can never be interpreted as an open space to welcome children with some difficulty, where differentiated work can be developed, with a view to including them in school; because the idea of inclusion must be like what Levi Vygotsky (1896-1934) advocated, *social inclusion*, that is, making the individual capable of living their life to the full and with less dependence on others; enjoying their existence, with dignity, just like everyone else and among them.

If the school does not pay attention to this, it fails to promote inclusion, in its humanistic perspective and transforms the child into a slave of the institution, under a euphemism of care, which is nothing more than overprotection, a state of suffocation of the individual freedom, which ends up ending in imminent failure, where imminent success and empirical and epistemic advances could be obtained, with regard to the treatment and technical application of efficient pedagogical practices to this specific target audience.

Jesus (2002) states that, in order to consolidate broad and pragmatic thinking about Inclusive Education in regular schools, it is necessary

Build, together with the school, an inclusive reflective practice that incorporates the generation of knowledge itself. The perspective was to work in the daily pedagogical practice of the school through various strategies, with the goal of producing a self-forming reflection (...) [...] based on the conception of education for all students, including those with special needs , it can be seen that the collaborative support approach, in which each party seeks to know, understand and build with the other, constituted a fundamental device for a transformative educational practice (p. 93).

When reflecting on the scope of meaning and significance of the inclusive education process, we are considering the diversity of learners and their right to equity. It is about equalizing opportunities, guaranteeing everyone - including people with disabilities and those with high skills and giftedness, the right to learn to learn, learn to do, learn to be and learn to live together (CARVALHO, 2005) .

The National Education Plan (PNE), prescribed in art. 214 of the 1988 Constitution and reaffirmed in the National Education Guidelines and Bases Law no. 9,394/96, art. 9th, § I and art. 87, § 1, is considered a political instrument of systematized priorities and content, through which the Federal government, through the Ministry of Education, coordinates, controls and supervises education throughout the country, at all levels of education.

In line with the National Education Plan, the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education, Law No. 9,394/96, in art. 58 § 1, guarantees that there will be, when necessary, specialized support services, in the regular school, to meet the peculiarities of the Special Education clientele (BRASIL, 1996). Still the art. 59, of the same Law, recommends that education systems must ensure students with special educational needs:

- I - specific curriculum, methods, resources and organization to meet your needs;
- II- terminality specific to those who did not reach the level required to complete primary education, due to their disabilities; and acceleration to complete the school program for the gifted in less time;
- III - teachers with appropriate specialization at secondary or higher level, for specialized service, as well as regular education teachers trained to integrate these students into common classes (BRASIL, 1996, sp).

As presented by law, students with special needs have guaranteed rights with regard to care appropriate to each specificity. In this sense, CNE/CEB resolution n° 2/2001 defines the access of these students, giving them the subjective right to quality education.

From this perspective, CNE/CEB resolution n° 2/2001 establishes National Guidelines for Special Education in Basic Education, in art. 2nd, highlights that “education systems must enroll all students, and schools are responsible for organizing themselves to serve students with special educational needs, ensuring the necessary conditions for quality education for all” (Brazil, 2001, sp) .

The National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (1996) defines Special Education as a type of school education that is offered preferably in the regular education network, for students with special needs (art. 58) and uses, interchangeably, the two terms presented to follow.

From this perspective, the target audience for Special Education students are served in the multifunctional resource rooms, as established in the National Special Education Policy from the perspective of Inclusive Education and in Decree No. 6,571/2008.

The National Education Conference – CONAE/ 2010, Law No. 13,005/2014, which establishes the National Education Plan – PNE, in item III, paragraph 1, of article 8, determines that:

The States, the Federal District and the Municipalities guarantee that specific needs in special education are met, ensuring an inclusive educational system at all levels, stages and modalities. Based on this assumption, goal 4 and respective strategies aim to universalize, for people with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high abilities/giftedness, in the age group from 4 to 17 years old, access to basic education and specialized educational care.

AEE is preferably offered in the regular education network, and can be carried out through agreements with specialized institutions, without compromising the inclusive educational system (BRASIL, 2014, sp).

Special Education is not used ; only *Specialized Educational Service* . Therefore, so that LDBEN is not considered incompatible with the Constitution, it is necessary to understand the term “Special Education as a teaching modality that offers Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE)” (FÁVERO, 2004, p. 84).

When talking about AEE, teaching practice in this context must be highlighted. Therefore, the teacher must constantly seek professional updating, aiming to improve the work developed with PAEE students.

THE NEED FOR CONTINUING TRAINING OF TEACHERS WHO WORK IN AEE

In relation to the continuing training of teachers, Chimentão (2009) states that, it “[...] has been understood as a permanent process of improving the knowledge necessary for professional teaching activity, carried out after initial training, with the aim of ensuring better quality teaching for students” (p. 3).

In the legal guidelines, specifically in Resolution No. 2 of July 1, 2015 in its article 16, it is found that:

Continuing training comprises collective, organizational and professional dimensions, as well as rethinking the pedagogical process, knowledge and values, and involves extension activities, study groups, pedagogical meetings, courses, programs and actions in addition to the minimum training required for the exercise of teaching in basic education, with the main purpose of reflecting on educational practice and the search for technical, pedagogical, ethical and political improvement of the teaching professional (BRASIL, 2015, sp).

It appears that, with the absence of continued training, there is inequality in the quality of teaching, as some teachers do not innovate their educational practices and permanent study, combined with the symbolic exchange of pedagogical and didactic experiences, favors a deeper understanding of the themes that involve teaching. praxis and the development of thought, leading to solid knowledge about the action and the target audience, how they behave, what needs they present, what adaptations are necessary and possible.

Regarding teacher training, Alarcão (2003) states that the teacher must consider himself in a constant process of self-training and professional identification. The author also adds that he has to be a reflective teacher in a reflective professional community.

Gabardo (2006, p. 41), states that “the role of the education professional indicates the teacher as a reflective, researcher, critical and participatory being”. According to the author, the reflective teacher must continually analyze and evaluate their pedagogical experience according to the social context, and thus, seek new alternatives to solve problems and overcome difficulties.

From this same perspective, Garcia states that

Continuing teacher training favors research questions and theoretical and practical proposals that study the processes in which teachers are involved, and that allows them to intervene professionally in the development of their teaching, the curriculum and the school (1999, p. 22) .

Therefore, teacher training, whether initial or continued, constitutes a relevant topic for study and research, in order to promote the conditions for the school to effectively fulfill “its function of teaching and 'training' individuals who are active in building a society characterized by equity and justice” (BARRETO 2011, p. 205).

THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF SPECIALIZED EDUCATIONAL SERVICE IN MULTIFUNCTIONAL RESOURCE ROOMS

In fact, it is known that Specialized Educational Assistance aims to guarantee satisfactory support to students who need it. Furthermore, it is

A teaching modality that covers all levels, degrees and stages of the school journey and aims, among others, to identify the needs and possibilities of students with disabilities, develop care plans, aiming at access and participation in the schooling process in common schools, assist students with disabilities in the opposite shift to that in which they attend the common room, produce and/or indicate teaching materials and resources that guarantee accessibility for students with disabilities to curricular content, monitor the use of these resources in the classroom , checking its functionality, its applicability and the need for possible adjustments, and guiding families and teachers regarding the resources used by the student (SARTORETTO; SARTORETTO, 2010, p. 2).

As the authors explain, the resource room is a place for learning, where different types of pedagogical and didactic experiences can be carried out, all of which have the general objective of knowing the limits of each participant, creating possibilities for systematic advancement in terms of intellectual and cognitive skills and also develop motor, sensory and psychological skills. Therefore, those who integrate there, in the willingness to carry out the work, must be aware that they are inside a living laboratory, which demands as much or more

from professionals than the regular classroom, considering that, everything produced there, must be integrated into the annals of the institution, in the form of teaching material, arising from experience and pedagogical praxis.

Regarding functional resource rooms, Pereira (2020) argues that,

The service provided in this space differs from that offered by a regular school, as it is not characterized as an eminently clinical service, but has a typically educational characteristic. Therefore, the primary objective of this service is to provide the student enrolled in the common school target audience for special education with the recognition of their potential and limitations, leading them to perceive themselves as capable of creating strategies to solve their problems and to become see it as a Being with rights, being capable of producing knowledge and transforming your reality.

There are several benefits that can be developed in the multifunctional resource room, in parallel, and that help the development of teaching in the regular classroom.

Some of the advantages that were associated with the special class can be enhanced in the resource room, as work with small groups is encouraged, allowing better monitoring of the student, favoring more individualized learning trajectories under the supervision of a teacher with specific training. In the case of the resource room, the great advantage is that this process is capable of continuous alternation with that developed in the common classroom (BAPTISTA, 2011, p. 70).

With regard to the evaluation of students who are the target audience for special education, two distinct purposes are considered: one of them aims to identify the need for assistance for each student and the other seeks to plan teaching in order to meet each specificity. In this sense, the assessment focuses on identifying whether or not a given student has any special needs, global developmental disorder or giftedness/high abilities to then define their potential eligibility for AEE services (VELTRONE, 2011).

In addition to pedagogical practices, it is worth highlighting whether the results of the work

They indicated as positive aspects of AEE the family participation, small classes and the conception of the Resource Room as a space that makes it possible to understand the student's learning process, configuring an environment that promotes development, fundamental to enable educational inclusion. The negative aspects highlighted were insufficient continuing education courses, lack of material and pedagogical resources, absence of a multidisciplinary team and the need for bi-teaching in common classes. The main strategies adopted in teaching practice were partnership with the family, coordination between Resource Room teachers and common classes and the promotion of a pleasant and motivating environment for the student to stay. Regarding continuing education, the importance of courses, day-to-day life

with the student, lectures and exchange of professional experiences was highlighted (CORREA, et. al., 2020, p. 09)

Given this, family collaboration with the school becomes essential, aiming at the student's development in the teaching-learning process. Therefore, it can be said that the family and the school form a team, which need to have the same objectives in relation to the student's progress.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The considerations made throughout this research indicate that there is still a need for training for professionals who work in this area, considering that the training of teachers who work in the educational process needs to be continuous, in order to improve knowledge and, mainly, practices educational.

The findings of this study show that teachers in specialized educational services still need continued training, in order to increase the possibilities of dynamics in the teaching and learning process. It is essential for the teacher to study in-depth, to plan appropriately for each need presented by the target student, so that teaching and learning take place efficiently and effectively.

The research results also indicate that resource rooms provide development in individualized trajectories, also supporting the exercise of social practices. In addition to what has been discussed so far, it is concluded that it is necessary to understand resource rooms as a place that seeks to guarantee the necessary support for students with special needs. However, it is worth highlighting the family's collaboration so that the student properly attends classes in the off-shift, designed to provide the student with the necessary assistance.

This study also opens up perspectives for new research, in order to verify the potential and abilities of students with special needs with the applicability of different methodologies in resource rooms, considering the need for reflections on the theme discussed throughout this study.

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